

Reconceptualizing the “economic dimension” of sustainability based on a review of theories of the firm across economic schools of thought

Dr. Michael Curran

Department of Food System Sciences (FSS)

Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), 5070 Frick, Switzerland

Contact: michael.curran@fibl.org

Summary

Sustainability science (SS) has always had a curious relationship with economics. It emerged from the “growth debate” of the 1970s, where ecological economics (promoting “post-growth” theories of economic prosperity based on biophysical limits, sufficiency and wellbeing) criticized neoclassical economics for their “green growth” focus on substitution, efficiency and welfare. In the ensuing period, proponents of “green growth” shouted the loudest, and an “economic dimension” was added to the definition of sustainability, paradoxically reintroducing growth (green or otherwise) as a policy goal (e.g. Brundtland Report, SDG Target 8.1). This highlights a conflict between competing “schools of thought” in economics (in this case ecological and neoclassical), which are often characterized by contradictory assumptions and conflicting explanations of economic phenomena. Theory choice clearly affects how economic performance is measured, yet there is little to no coherent economic theory justifying the choice of criteria and indicators in many indicator-based sustainability assessment frameworks (in agriculture and beyond). To help achieve this aim, this study reviews micro-economic theories of the firm across economic schools of thought (new and old institutionalist, behavioural, managerial, neoclassical, neo-Austrian, post-Keynesian, feminist, ecological and Marxian). Theories are analysed to identify explanations of how firms behave and what functions they fulfil in the economy. The results are compared to typical criteria employed in SA, covering 16 existing Sustainability Assessment Tools (SATs). The findings suggest clear choices must be made when theories conflict, strongly impacting SAT design. More importantly, the results suggest that economic, governance and social dimensions are largely inseparable should be abandoned in favour of a coherent “systemic” approach that eliminated dimensional boundaries.

I. Introduction

I.1 What is “economic sustainability”?

The questions of what the economy *is*, how it *functions* and which *purpose(s)* it serves (or should serve) are central to the concept of “economic sustainability”. The concept of sustainability is, by definition, normative and requires prior definition of what is to be sustained (e.g. human flourishing, satisfaction of needs or raising incomes) in relation to the key assets, functions and processes that sustain it (e.g. planetary life-support systems, exhaustible resources and so forth). A logical way of approaching and defining economic sustainability would thus be to align our understanding of the economy, driven by the science of economics, with the normative concerns and goals of sustainability. The latter has been researched *ad nauseum* within fields such as Sustainability Science, Earth System Science, Climate Science or Conservation Biology, with a huge body of research highlighting the problems society faces, framed in various ways, such as planetary boundaries (Steffen et al. 2015), energetic constraints (Ayres and Warr 2009) or material scarcities (Wiedmann et al. 2013). Yet, when we look through the history of economics, and scan the current diversity of perspectives across different “schools of thought” in the field ¹ (e.g. Neoclassical, Austrian, post-Keynesian, Marxian or Ecological Economics), one would be forgiven for getting the impression that there is very little agreement amongst economists about what the economy *is* and how it *functions*.

The mainstream view

The “orthodox” or “mainstream” neoclassical theory positions itself as a “positive” science of human behaviour, or more specifically as the study of individual choice under a given set of (e.g. budget, time, resource) constraints. In this vein, one of the most established definitions of economics was provided by Lionel Robbins (1932) almost a century ago as:

“...the science which studies human behaviour as a relationship between ends and scarce means which have alternative uses” (Robbins 1932 p. 85)

This narrow definition reduces economics to the study of individual behaviour and reduced our understanding of the economy to all aspects of human choice that balance ends and means in a “rational” way. The definition of rationality continues to be widely debated (e.g. formal rationality, bounded rationality), but neoclassical theory largely focuses on utility maximization under conditions of perfect information and a set of fixed preferences that are revealed in the market rather than being continuously formed. The primary way to study human choice is economics became synonymous with analysis of markets, which is essentially how the economy has been conceived since the marginalist revolution of Walras, Jevons and co. Neoclassical theory thus begins with the premise of a buyer and seller and a market at or close to equilibrium. Other aspects

¹ For an overview of the different “heterodox” schools, see Lavoie (2022 p. 7)

that influence wealth creation or appropriation (non-market institutions, the state, power, social relationships, ethics etc.) were largely relegated to understanding how they promote or distort the correct functioning of markets.

Robbins' definition precludes the study of objective measures of value (e.g. the material basis for production, ecological processes and functions, labour as a source of value or objective measures of wellbeing) to the chagrin of Marxian, degrowth and ecological economists. It also reduces the prominence of macroeconomics and political economy, unless they can be addressed with theories that take individual choice and rational behaviour as a starting point. Neoclassical behavioural economics has applied this logic in an attempt to explain a wide range of human behaviours, including popular accounts of the economization of everyday phenomena (e.g. Levitt and Dubner 2008). At the macro level, the establishment of "micro foundations" in macroeconomics was considered a small revolution in the 1970s, when the "Lucas critique" joined micro- and macroeconomics to develop a new class of macroeconomic models (DSGE models) that dominated the field until their failure during the Great Recession of 2007/2008 (Keen 2013). In resource and environmental economics, microeconomic foundations form the basis for theories of intertemporal choice based on discounted utilitarianism (e.g. the Ramsey equation), which treats inter-generational distribution from the perspective of an "infinitely-lived consumer" (Roemer 2011). As a result, the goal of the economy can largely be reduced to meeting the aggregated preferences of individuals and is typically reduced to a single metric of monetary value.

This focus on maximizing aggregate value was justified by Nicholas Kaldor (1939) in the first half of the century, who embraced Pigou's division of welfare economics into a productive and distributive component. Kaldor strongly argued to elevate the former and largely ignore the latter as a primary concern of economic science:

"The first, and *far the more important part*, should include all those propositions for increasing social welfare which relate to the increase in aggregate production; all questions concerning the stimulation of employment, the equalisation of social net products, and the equalisation of prices with marginal costs, would fall under this heading... In the second part, *concerning distribution, the economist should not be concerned with "prescriptions" at all*, but with the relative advantages of different ways of carrying out certain political ends. For it is quite impossible to decide on economic grounds what particular pattern of income-distribution maximises social welfare." – Kaldor (1939), emphasis added

Kaldor's assertion, and complementary work by John Hicks (1939), led to the famous "Kaldor-Hicks criterion" in (benefit-cost) policy analysis (De Scitovszky 1941), that an economic policy to increase aggregate production is desirable if the winners *could in theory* compensate the losers, and still come out in the positive:

"There is no interpersonal comparison of satisfactions involved in judging any policy designed to increase the sum total of wealth just because any such policy *could* be carried out in a way as to secure unanimous consent." – Kaldor (1939), emphasis added

These neoclassical foundations on the definition of economics, and the purpose of the economy, have largely persisted (not unchallenged) to this day. Neoclassical theory is

still concerned with the maximization of aggregated output (or profits or utility depending on the scale of analysis). From this perspective we could say that the purpose of economic sustainability as a policy would be the traditional allocational efficiency to maximize the growth of aggregate output, as is the focus of growth theory, while also targeting price stability and full employment in the policy domain. This definition of economic sustainability is therefore just a re-formulation of growth theory, with “sustainability” only being of importance when exhaustible resources and scarce ecological functions enter the picture. The sub-field of Resource and Environmental Economics attempts to explain how the economy reacts to sustainability shocks and scarcities, largely following some variation of Hotelling’s rule, specifying the rate at which the value (price) of an exhaustible resource must appreciate to clear the market and stimulate the search for substitutes (Solow 1974). And missing prices are dealt with through shadow pricing (environmental valuation), which is a field within itself (e.g. Atkinson et al. 2012) and has attracted its own criticisms by those who challenge the monistic (i.e. a single value metric) conception of value and argue for a more “plural” approach to valuation (e.g. Martinez-Alier et al. 1998, Arias-Arévalo et al. 2018, Christie et al. 2019). While this is a gross simplification of the neoclassical position, one can broadly summarize that the starting point of neoclassical analyses is of an economy of interlinked markets at or close to equilibrium, it functions according to microeconomic foundations of households and businesses (risk-adjusted profit and utility maximization, cost-minimization and so forth) and the aim is to maximize aggregate monetary value.

Heterodox perspectives

In contrast, so-called “heterodox” (or alternative) schools of thought in economics present a completely different picture of what the economy is, how it functions and what purposes it serves (or should serve). Take the opening statement of Frederic Lee’s posthumously published synthesis of “Heterodox” microeconomic theory:

“Economics as a discipline is a specialized, scientific, factual body of knowledge that endeavours to develop theoretical explanations of real economic activities that connect acting persons *qua* households with the flow of goods and services needed to sustain their existence and promote their well-being over time. Thus economic activities are enmeshed with others to form an interdependent, intertwined system of production and consumption. Similarly, acting persons are not isolated, but are enmeshed in various social relationships that cannot be stripped away... that is, *economics is defined as the science of the social provisioning process.*” – Lee and Jo (2018 p. 1)

This framing of economics is particularly wide and can be interpreted to span much of the social (and even natural) sciences. Lee continues with a definition of the economy as:

“...an emergent system of social-economic activities that generate an array of surplus goods and services (over what is used up in production) needed to sustain households and their social relationships, and thus society as a whole – in short, the economy is about social provisioning.” (Lee and Jo 2018 p. 1)

The concept of emergence (i.e. phenomena that exhibit a “more than the sum of its parts” behaviour when aggregated) reflects a key point of difference between orthodox and heterodox schools. The heterodox schools largely recognize the role of system complexity and non-linear dynamics in generating macro-scale phenomena that cannot be derived from micro-scale behaviours (the fallacy of composition). Lavoie (2022 p. 18) presents several “macro-paradoxes” as evidence of emergent behaviour at the macro scale, such as the “paradox of thrift” (higher savings rates lead to reduced output or growth) or the “paradox of public deficits” (government deficits raise private profits). This heavily complicates attempts at establishing a micro-macro link through simple forms of aggregation (Spangenberg 2005, Gräbner and Kapeller 2017). Note however, that emergence does not invalidate aggregation as such, just certain forms of it, such as common methods in neoclassical models like representative agent analysis and common approaches in welfare economics.

More broadly, heterodox perspectives broaden our understanding of the economy as a system of social provisioning that is embedded within a wider set of social and ecological relations. These include material and energy exchange with the surrounding ecosystem (Ecological Economics), class struggles mediated by the power of ownership of productive assets (Marxian), unequal gender relations (Feminist) and broader institutional structures that are leveraged for power and profit (“Old” Institutionalism). These wider influences effect the choices available to agents and groups of agents, who form preferences *ad hoc* based on a partial and subjective information, while engaging in satisficing behaviour to cope with persistent, strong uncertainty in the sense of Night (1921). The agents in turn reproduce or transform this social structure through their practices and behaviours (Behavioural Economics), and these routines may be evolved over time in response to changing selection pressures in the economic environment (Evolutionary Economics). In other words, the economy is a mix of exchange systems that may be private and competitive (e.g. markets, barter), redistributive (e.g. households, firms, states) or reciprocal (e.g. friendships, traditions, gifting) in nature (Polanyi 1944).

Regarding the purpose of the economy, while some schools aim primarily at better realism and explanation (e.g. post-Keynesian), many heterodox theories (apart from perhaps Austrian) also argue for a more normative and direct purpose for the economy, such as meeting human needs within planetary boundaries, achieving subjective wellbeing, human flourishing, rewarding human labour, pursuing justice or promoting human development (e.g. Sen 2005, Jackson 2009, O’Neill et al. 2018). This represents a strong break from the “positive” assertion of neoclassical economists that aggregate production can be interpreted as a neutral measure of welfare.

1.2 Sustainability assessment of organizations and the “economic dimension” of sustainability

The emergence of the concept of sustainability is largely attributed to the “growth debate” kicked-off by the publication of the “Limits to Growth” study (Meadows et al. 1972). The

original idea was largely about environmental resources and ecological functions. The economy did not feature in the list of things that required sustaining. In contrast, the economy, and its apparent need to grow in order to remain stable, was considered the main cause of *un*-sustainability! The “social” and “economic” dimensions that characterize the “three pillars approach” to sustainability assessment arrived later in the debate with little theoretical or conceptual justification (Purvis et al. 2019). Sustainability science (SS) emerged at the turn of the century from these various influences (Clark et al. 2005, de Vries 2012). And there is an ongoing discussion about the appropriate economic theory to inform sustainability science, with some researchers calling for a rejection of neoclassical theory (Diesendorf et al. 2024). The authors justify this based on the argument above, that neoclassical economic and its dependence on growth to achieve economic aims, represents the main challenge for sustainability, not a metric of success (Daly 1997a). But they also cite conceptual flaws in neoclassical theory, recommending a revision of the theory largely in the direction of what is described as “heterodox” in the previous section.

For sustainability scientists, who apply sustainability frameworks, indicators or develop and use “sustainability assessment tools” (SATs), this theoretical schism is of particular importance. In the agriculture and food sector, there is a growing demand for operational SATs to guide value chain actors towards sustainability outcomes or assess particular policies and practices. SATs attempt to capture a wide scope of impacts of agricultural operators (i.e. farms and other value chain actors) across sustainability dimensions (usually social, environmental, economic and governance). Dimensions are generally disaggregated to specific targets (biodiversity, climate change, labour conditions, wellbeing) and indicators (Bockstaller et al. 2009, Singh et al. 2009, Binder et al. 2010, Schader et al. 2014a). Unlike other integrated assessments (e.g. environmental LCA), sustainability assessment tools (SAT) combine a normative framework with a multi-dimension and multi-criteria assessment structure and apply a mixed method (quantitative and qualitative) and solution-orientated approach (Binder et al. 2010, Sala et al. 2013, 2015). Examples of farm level SATs include RISE (Thalmann and Grenz 2013), the SMART-Farm Tool (Schader et al. 2016), SOSTARE (Paracchini et al. 2015), “IDEA4” (Zahm et al. 2024) and “SALCAsustain” (Roesch et al. 2021).

While SATs can be valuable tools to measure sustainability hotspots of farm management, the range of addressed topics results in a trade-off between scope and precision for any single criterion (Schader et al. 2014, de Olde et al. 2018). There is also no common definition of sustainability despite notable efforts to build consensus (Pintér et al. 2012, FAO 2014a, e.g. 2018). This has resulted in different interpretations of what sustainability entails by tool developers. As a result, the same SAT might differ in the level of detail across criteria, and different SATs might differ in overall framework (criteria, hierarchy, aggregation methods and indicators). This can potentially lead to contradictory results for decision-makers, both in using the same tool, or in comparing tools. Thus, how economic theory is interpreted, which schools of thought are given prominence in the case of tensions/conflicts, matters greatly, but has not been discussed

extensively in the literature on tools and operational methods in sustainability assessment.

1.3 Research aims and questions

The present paper aims to address this research gap between conflicting theory in economics on the one hand and the requirements of SAT developers and users on the other. I aim to present a plural perspective on economic theories of the firm across a wide range of “schools of thought” in economics. The firm represents an important scale of analysis for the development and application of SATs, and has been the focus of previous research in this direction (Lozano et al. 2015). In the agri-food sector, multiple tools are applied at the farm scale or below (farm enterprise, parcel, cropping system), making the link to theory of the firm particularly promising. Key research questions are:

1. How do different schools of thought in economics conceptualize the firm, in terms of purpose, main behaviours, functioning and interaction with the wider economy?
2. How can these theories inform the choice of criteria and indicators for applied field of sustainability assessment?
3. What conflicts or knowledge gaps exist between theories, and do these have operational implications for indicator-based sustainability assessment, such as ruling out certain sets of methods as theoretically incompatible?

2. Methods

2.1 Literature search and reviewed publications

Key literature in the theory of the firm was reviewed in a narrative approach to capture the main theoretical strands. I started with several targeted searches in scientific databases (namely, Google Scholar and Web of Science) with the key words “theory of the firm” and “economics” and the name of the various schools of thought. The various schools were first identified in an initial set of core literature (Dietrich and Krafft 2012, Lozano et al. 2015, Lavoie 2022). From there, I screened the result and used cross-citations within the initial set of studies to identify new material. A systematic approach was not desired, because a representative view of the literature was not the aim of the research, rather I was interested in summarizing core conceptual accounts of predefined positions related to different schools of thought. The list of the main literature sources associated used to capture the various school of thought are presented in the appendix **Error! Reference source not found.** The research aims to include the following schools of thought: Neoclassical Economics (NCE), New Institutional Economics (NIE), Austrian Economics (Austrian), Old Institutional Economics (OIE), Post-Keynesian Economics (PKE), Feminist Economics (Feminist), Degrowth and Ecological Economics (Ecological), Evolutionary Economics (Evolutionary) and Behavioural Economics (Behavioural).

2.2 Sustainability frameworks

In a second step, I aimed to contrast my summary of economic theory with the objects of evaluation in existing sustainability assessment tools (SATs). I collected a balanced sample of SATs using several recent systematic reviews of indicator, evaluation frameworks and operational tools (Bonisoli et al. 2018, Eichler Inwood et al. 2018, Lampridi et al. 2019, Arulnathan et al. 2020, Chopin et al. 2021, Subedi et al. 2025). After scanning for potential tools, they were narrowed down if: a) they assessed all three traditional dimensions of sustainability (economic, environmental and social), b) methods were published in a peer-reviewed publication or book chapter and c) were applied or intended for use at the farm scale or below (i.e. cropping system, parcel, farm enterprise or parcel scale). To the resulting list, I included two indicator frameworks at the food system scale in order to explore whether the topics evaluated were fundamentally different across scales (Heredia-R et al. 2024, Acs et al. 2025).

After identifying suitable frameworks, I searched each methodological document and extracted a dataset of criteria assessed at each level of the assessment hierarchy along with a list of indicators under each criterion. These frameworks were then harmonized by aligning them into a common system of “dimensions”, “themes” and “sub-themes”, in line with the SAFA framework (FAO 2014a). Similar sub-themes were grouped and reclassified according to a common name. The themes and dimensions were also adapted where necessary. Finally, I aligned the final harmonized framework to the different theories of the firm where possible, to understand how the empirical tools relate to key concepts in the theory of the firm.

3. Results

3.1 Schools of thought on the theory of the firm

I focused on a smaller sub-set of more “complete” theories of the firm in this article (Neoclassical, NIE, Austrian, PKE/OIE, Ecological and Marxian). Behavioural and Evolutionary theories were considered only for specific areas, because they also inform much of the heterodox schools. Feminist theory does not have a complete model of the firm and is left out of the main analysis but included in the discussion for specific issues relating to gender aspects. An overview of the main features of the different theories studied are shown in Table 1. In the next sections, these various theories are summarized.

Table I. Summary of the different theories of the firm considered in the study. The table omits feminist, behavioural and evolutionary theories, which are discussed in the text, but are incomplete in several areas of the table (pricing, returns to scale, behaviour etc.).

School of thought	Neoclassical	New Institutional	Austrian	PKE/Old-inst.	Ecological	Marxian
Economic function	Production function	Increase efficiency	Capture rent	Self-preservation	Biophysical transform.	Exploit labour power
Equilibrium	Assumed	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
Goals	Profit max.	Profit max.	Profit max.	Growth max.	Biophysical transformation	Capital accumulation
Rationality	Formal	Instrumental	Subjective	Bounded	Bounded	Instrumental
Information	Perfect	Imperfect, biased	Imperfect, biased	Imperfect, biased	Imperfect, biased	Imperfect, biased
Decision uncertainty	Weak (probability)	Weak (probability)	Strong (ignorance)	Strong (ignorance)	Strong (ignorance)	Strong (ignorance)
Returns to scale (short-run)	Diminishing	Diminishing	Contextual	Constant	Diminishing (ecologically)	Diminishing (socially)
Capacity utilization	Full	Contextual	Not specified	Underutilization	Overutilization (ecological)	Overutilization
Competition	Perfect competition	Contextual	Dynamic competition	Oligopoly/Monopoly	Oligopoly/Monopoly	Oligopoly/Monopoly
Pricing behaviour	Marginal pricing	Marginal pricing	Entrepreneurial judgement	Normal-cost pricing/ strategic pricing	Corrected prices (ecologically)	Strategic pricing

3.2 An overview of the main theories of the firm

The classicals viewed economics as devoted to the macro study of a) the production of an economic surplus and b) the distribution of the surplus among different factors and (classes of) people. Focusing on the internal workings of individual firms was considered irrelevant, with the assumption that firms employed fixed amounts of production factors (“fixed coefficients”) and constant returns to scale (i.e. constant profit margins as output grows). In this respect, the classicals had no theory of the firm, which were assumed to be passive links in the chain connecting production to consumption, with little agency to alter the means of production, its productivity or profitability (Walker 2016). Firm boundaries did not exist, because the constant returns assumption made size (and thus the number of firms) irrelevant. This assumption was carried over by the early marginalists (e.g. Clark, Wicksteed and Walras), meaning firms played no role in determining general equilibrium of the macroeconomy (Arrow 1971).

An exception to classical ignorance on the working of the firm was the neoclassical contribution of Alfred Marshall (Marshall 1890), whose theory of partial equilibrium was dependent on firms adjusting their level of output based on changing the proportions (i.e. coefficients) of fixed (i.e. capital, land) and variable (i.e. labour) production factors in the short run (Williams 1978). Marshall’s definition was functions and did not explain what firms are or why they exist at all in an economy presumed to be made up of individuals. Instead, Marshall assumed a specific behaviour (profit maximization under conditions of diminishing returns) to create the conditions for market equilibrium. The firm’s purpose in this early literature was therefore “overcoming disequilibrium” by taking advantage of unequal rates of profit (Arrow 1971). The “who”, “why” and “how” of firm theory, along with explaining the diversity of firms (from small family operations to large vertically integrated corporations) was largely left blank until the first half of the 20th century with the work of Knight (1921) and Coase (1937). Historically viewed, different theories can be split into “old”, that focus on the question of what firms *do* in the economy, and “new”, that attempt to explain what firms *are* as institutions and why they exist. Walker (2016 p. 4) dates the division where research questions shifted from the “doing” to the “being” as the 1970s, where a renewed interest in Coase and an expanding literature devoted to transaction costs and contracts (NIE) provided a novel explanation for why firms exist in an economy assumed by neoclassical theory to be made up of atomistic individuals going about the business of producing, trading and consuming.

In the following sections, an overview of each theory is provided as a basis for identifying links to how firms are assessed in Sustainability Science, specifically concerning firm-level SATs. Specifically, theories are investigated based on the theories position on a) economic function of the firm, b) equilibrium/disequilibrium, c) primary goals of the firm, d) the rationality of decision-making, e) the availability of information, f) the reflection of decision uncertainty, g) assumptions on (short-run) returns to scale, h) capacity utilization of fixed capital (capital, factories, land etc.), i) competitive dynamics of the market and j) pricing behaviour.

The Neoclassical (Marshallian) firm

Neoclassical theory posits that firms are rational, profit-maximizing entities in markets typically characterized by perfect competition, but the theory can also be applied to various degrees of monopoly/imperfect competition. In the short run, firms face diminishing marginal returns due to changing ratios of fixed capital (e.g. machinery, factories, land) to variable inputs (e.g. labour, fertilizer, pesticides). This leads to a U-shaped average cost curve (Mas-Colell et al. 1995). The primary goal of the firm is profit maximization, and agents are assumed to act with formal rationality and perfect information (Debreu 1959). Later extensions introduce asymmetric information and the minimization of weak uncertainty (probabilistic risk; Knight 1921). Under perfect competition, firms are price-takers, and pricing behaviour is reduced to setting price at marginal cost. Under monopoly, they equalize marginal revenue with marginal cost (Tirole 1988). Capacity utilization of fixed capital is generally assumed to be full under perfect competition, pushing first into diminishing returns to increase output in response to increases in demand. The economic function of the firm is to maximize output via the efficient use of inputs, given current prices and technological constraints (Coase 1937). Markets tend toward equilibrium and firms earn normal profits under perfect competition (or economic rents under imperfect competition).

The New Institutional firm

The New Institutional Economics (NIE) frames firms as governance structures designed to minimize transaction costs in an environment of bounded rationality and opportunism. In the short run, returns to scale are constrained by transaction costs (e.g. contracting, monitoring, enforcement), leading firms to adapt production levels based on efficiency concerns, and are diminishing with respect to management capacity (Williamson 1975). The primary goal of the firm is transaction cost minimization, which may manifest as other goals (profit/growth maximization) depending on institutional context (Williamson 1985). Rationality is limited and adaptive, and firms make decisions under cognitive constraints and imperfect information, relying on heuristics, routines, and governance structures to navigate weak uncertainty (North 1990), drawing inspiration from behavioural theory (Simon 1955). Competition is shaped by institutional frameworks (e.g., property rights, contract enforcement) and firms compete not only on price or quality but also on efficiency (Williamson 1975). Information is asymmetric and costly to acquire, leading to opportunistic behaviour mitigated through contracts, hierarchies, or reputational mechanisms (Williamson 1985). The economic function of the firm is to increase efficiency after accounting for transaction costs and sources of risk (Coase 1937). Firms in competitive markets may engage in marginal cost pricing, while those in hierarchical structures use other pricing behaviours (e.g. administered prices) to reduce uncertainty (Williamson 1975). Capacity utilization reflects trade-offs between internal production (hierarchies) and external sourcing (markets), with underutilization often resulting from coordination costs or contractual hazards (Coase 1937). NIE rejects the neoclassical notion of market equilibrium, arguing that markets and firms are in a continuous state of adaptation to changing institutional

environments, with outcomes shaped by path dependence, power asymmetries, and evolutionary processes (North 1990).

The Austrian firm

Austrian economics posits the firm in terms of entrepreneurs (i.e. agents with innovative ideas but no financing) navigating dynamic, uncertain markets. It rejects equilibrium, framing markets as perpetually evolving through entrepreneurial discovery and error correction (Langlois 2013). The firm's economic function is to coordinate dispersed knowledge and allocate resources through entrepreneurial action (von Mises 1949). Its primary goal is to seek rents within a perpetual disequilibrium, involving discovery rather than optimization (Lewin and Phelan 2000). As a consequence, short-run returns to scale depend on entrepreneurial judgement in the sense of Schumpeter (Schumpeter 2000) and thus are context-dependent. Capacity utilization reflects entrepreneurial foresight and market signals, often marked by errors and adjustments (von Mises 1949). Rationality is subjective and adaptive, grounded in local knowledge and trial-and-error learning. Competition involves discovery, where firms innovate or imitate, and monopolies may be temporary and contested (Rothbard 1962). Information is decentralized and imperfect, with entrepreneurs relying on market prices as knowledge guides, but under conditions of radical/fundamental/strong uncertainty (Knight 1921). Pricing is adaptive and subjective, based on expectations of consumer valuations rather than cost curves (Rothbard 1962).

The post-Keynesian firm

The post-Keynesian theory of the firm rejects neoclassical optimization and equilibrium, instead emphasizing historical time, uncertainty, power relations, and institutional contexts. In the short run, returns to scale are shaped by demand constraints and market uncertainties rather than technical efficiency (Lavoie 2022 Ch. 3). The primary goal of the firm is growth and market share maximization rather than short-term profit maximization. PKE draws from behavioural theory in basing firm decisions on multi-objective satisficing (Simon 1955), balancing growth and profitability to capture market share while meeting financial obligations, to ensure long-term survival (Eichner 1976). Rationality is bounded and procedural, with decisions made under "fundamental" or "strong" uncertainty (Knight 1921, Keynes 1937) where probabilities are unknown, leading firms to rely on rules of thumb, conventions, and "animal spirits". Competition is oligopolistic and power-laden, characterized by barriers to entry, administered prices, and non-price competition (Eichner 1976), with firms engaging in strategic interaction rather than rivalry. Information is imperfect and asymmetrical, with firms operating under radical uncertainty about future demand, costs, and competitor actions (Shackle 1972). The economic function of the firm is essentially to survive and continue production in an uncertain world, balancing financial stability, growth, and social legitimacy (Minsky 1975). Pricing behaviour is cost-based and administered, with firms setting prices via markups, with normal-cost pricing most frequent based on typical

rather than actual costs (Lavoie 2022 Ch. 3). Firms operate under excess capacity due to uncertain demand and sticky prices (Kalecki 1939), largely within the range of constant returns to scale (Lavoie 2022 Ch. 3). Post-Keynesians reject market equilibrium, arguing that economies are inherently unstable and path-dependent, with firms operating in disequilibrium states shaped by demand fluctuations, financial fragility, and institutional inertia (Minsky 1986, Lavoie 2009, 2022).

The Old Institutional firm

Old Institutional (OIE) theory of the firm rejects neoclassical assumptions of rationality and equilibrium, instead framing firms as socially embedded institutions shaped by historical context, power relations, and cultural norms. In the short run, returns to scale are influenced by institutionalized routines, labour relations, and power dynamics (Veblen 1904), resulting in suboptimal or path-dependent/contextual outcomes. The economic function of the firm is to coordinate production within a web of social relations, often serving as a site of conflict and negotiation. The goals of the firm extend beyond profit maximization to include survival, power accumulation, and social legitimacy (Galbraith 1967), often engaging in satisficing behaviour (Simon 1955) across multi-objective goals shaped by stakeholder conflicts. Rationality is bounded and socially constructed, with decisions driven by habits, norms, and institutional pressures rather than optimization (Jo 2019). Competition is viewed as a power-laden, evolutionary process rather than a neutral market mechanism, with firms competing not just on price or efficiency but through political influence, advertising, and control over resources. Information is imperfect and asymmetrically distributed, reflecting class and power inequalities, while decision uncertainty arises from institutional complexity and conflicting social interests. Pricing behaviour is “administrative” (Means 1972), shaped by strategy in the face of social conventions, power, and internal practices. Firms may set prices based on markups, customs, or collusive agreements. Capacity utilization reflects social and organizational constraints rather than cost minimization (Jo 2019). OIE rejects the notion of market equilibrium, arguing that economies are dynamic, historically contingent, and shaped by ongoing institutional change, with outcomes determined by power struggles and evolutionary processes rather than equilibrium forces. Old institutional theory is largely used as a foundation for post-Keynesian theory following the pricing theories of Means (1972) and Eichner (1976) in the 1970s (Lavoie 2022 Ch. 3).

The Marxian firm

The Marxist theory of the firm frames firms as sites of class struggle and capitalist accumulation, fundamentally shaped by the imperative to extract surplus value from labour and the anarchic, crisis-prone dynamics of capitalism (Brennan 2017). In the short run, returns to scale are constrained and diminishing due to worker resistance to exploitation through strikes, sabotage, or turnover (Braverman 1998). The economic function of the firm is to accumulate capital by exploiting labour and nature, reproducing capitalist relations (Marx 1999). Rationality is instrumental to class interests,

with capitalists exploiting labour and externalizing costs (e.g., pollution, social harms). Workers' rationality is shaped by collective resistance (Harvey 2014). Competition is anarchic and destructive, leading to overproduction, price wars, and crises (Marx 1999) and information is asymmetrical and weaponized in the class struggle. Decision uncertainty stems from capitalism's inherent instability as firms face unpredictable crises, labour unrest, and market fluctuations and is seen as "strong" or "fundamental" in nature (Knight 1921). Pricing behaviour reflects class power and monopoly tendencies: firms set prices to maximize surplus value, often through monopoly rents, administered prices, or collusion, like PKE and Old Institutionalism. Capacity utilization is driven by the need to maximize surplus value, often leading to overwork, underinvestment in maintenance, or unsafe conditions (Marx 1999). Marxist theory rejects market equilibrium due to capitalism's inherently instability due to crises of overaccumulation, underconsumption, and class conflict

The Ecological Economic firm

The ecological economics is not a complete theory with regards to returns to scale, pricing behaviour etc. But it does introduce a fundamental new element of thermodynamic constraints, material and energy exhaustion and limits imposed by key ecological functions like climate regulation (Georgescu-Roegen 1971, Daly 1997a, Farley et al. 2005). It borrows theories on firm behaviour from other schools of thought (e.g. of the firm, valuation or macro modelling), and this has caused significant debate within the field (Spash 2013, Pirgmaier 2017). A more "orthodox" wing adopt certain neoclassical theories and is associated with "Steady State Economics" (Daly 1992). A more radical wing that adopts heterodox theories is more aligned with "Degrowth" (Froese et al. 2023) or "Social Ecological Economics" (Spash 2011, Earl 2017). To save space, I will focus only on the novel aspects of the school. This includes a view of firms as sites of biophysical transformation into the satisfaction of human needs. Profit or growth maximization is seen as fundamentally unsustainability and therefore firms must operate within a non-growing (steady state, stationary, post-growth) economy in the aggregate, or act in ways that are compatible with zero-growth (Froese et al. 2023). Much of this involves countering contended "growth imperatives" (Richters and Siemoneit 2019). These imperatives may be explained by other theories discussed above, but the difference is that Ecological Economist largely see growth as a universally negative phenomenon, even if the benefits of growth are fairly distributed (in contrast to, e.g., Marxists or PKE who see growth, if equitable, as a positive thing). Diminishing or negative returns may dominate but are seen from a societal perspective as irreversible losses in the quality and availability of material and energetic resources and ecological functions (Daly, 1977). Scaling production, whether in the firm or economy, invariably leads to increased entropy and waste, offsetting economic gains (Georgescu-Roegen, 1971). Ecological Economics is normative, which is a necessity if absolute limits on production exist, because this creates an unavoidable problem of intra- and intergenerational distribution that is not present in neoclassical theory due to assumptions of substitutability (Daly 1997b). Therefore, firms *should* make decisions

under strong sustainability constraints (e.g. maintaining natural capital) rather than narrow economic optimization (e.g. Hankammer et al. 2021). Ecological economics rejects market equilibrium as a meaningful concept, arguing that economies must operate within dynamic but bounded ecological limits (Jackson 2009).

3.3 Sustainability frameworks and economic theory

The results of the sustainability framework review revealed an initial pool of 58 potential frameworks, indicator sets and operational SATs, only 17 were selected for final analysis after meeting the filtering criteria. To these, I added two studies at the food system scale (Heredia-R et al. 2024, Acs et al. 2025) to investigate whether the evaluated topics are fundamentally different across scales. This gave a total of 19 SATs included in the analysis (Table 2). These frameworks were harmonized by grouping together similar concepts embodied in the different elements of the evaluation hierarchy.

In the final column of Table 2, I provide some tentative links to the theories of the firm discussed above. These are elaborated in the discussion, where I also consider links between theories and sustainability themes in other sustainability dimensions (social and institutional, but also some elements of biophysical and ecological sustainability themes).

Table 2. Resulting harmonized framework and occurrence of specific themes and *indicanda* (sub-themes) in the respective studies. Selected, core areas of alignment between sustainability themes and economic schools of thought are listed in the final column (details in the main text).

Dimensions, themes and <i>indicanda</i>	AcS et al. (2025)	CLM-SAI (2014)	Craheix et al. (2016)	Heredia-R. et al. (2024)	Jones et al. (2024)	Meul et al. (2008)	Paracchini et al. (2015)	Peano et al. (2015)	Sadok et al. (2009)	Schader et al. (2016)	Talukder et al. (2017)	Thalmann and Grenz (2013)	Estienne et al. (2021)	Wezel et al. (2025)	Wilfart et al. (2023)	Zahm et al. (2024)	Theoretical alignment with different schools of thought
Economic distribution	x									x		x		x			Cyclical crises due to inequality (Marxian), income and distributional effects on aggregate demand (PKE)
Factor (functional) income distribution										x							
Inter-firm distribution	x													x			
Personal income distribution												x					
Economic vulnerability	x		x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x		x	x	x	Broad alignment to most schools of thought for issues of viability and financial distress.
Business income diversification			x	x			x	x		x				x	x		
Business income stability	x			x		x										x	Solidarity and cooperation only seen positively in some theories such as Marxian (e.g. cooperatives, state corporations) and degrowth theories (degrowth businesses, solidarity economics). Otherwise, cooperation generally seen as a form of collusion in almost all schools.
Financial stability				x								x					
Input stability										x							
Insurance				x													
Liquidity										x							
Production stability										x	x					x	
Risk perception and management										x							
Solidarity and cooperation										x				x			
Efficiency and productivity	x	x			x	x	x				x		x		x	x	
Economic and technical efficiency	x										x		x		x	x	
Productivity of capital							x										
Productivity of labour							x	x									

Dimensions, themes and <i>indicanda</i>	AcS et al. (2025)	CLIM-SAI (2014)	Craheix et al. (2016)	Heredia-R. et al. (2024)	Jones et al. (2024)	Meul et al. (2008)	Paracchini et al. (2015)	Peano et al. (2015)	Sadok et al. (2009)	Schader et al. (2016)	Talukder et al. (2017)	Thalmann and Grenz (2013)	Estienne et al. (2021)	Wezel et al. (2025)	Wilfart et al. (2023)	Zahm et al. (2024)	Theoretical alignment with different schools of thought
Productivity of land		x			x	x	x						x		x		countered by specific policies to spread the gains of productivity.
Entrepreneurship	x			x		x		x		x	x	x		x		x	Entrepreneurship and innovation widely recognized to contribute to firm performance and growth (Austrian). Ecological Economics embrace ILK, and challenge potential of innovation to achieve green growth.
Capacity development							x		x	x	x		x		x		
Environmental knowledge				x													
Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK)							x		x								
Innovation and adoption	x																
Strategic sustainability management	x					x				x							Wide alignment, but degrowth challenges the growth imperative of private investment.
Investment										x		x					
Capital stocks and infrastructure												x					
Long-ranging investment										x		x					Degrowth embrace (regional) biophysical autonomy, also seen as buffer against risk (“make or buy” trade-off in NIE).
Production autonomy			x											x			
Energy autonomy														x			
Material autonomy			x											x			
Workforce autonomy														x			Broad importance of cost-minimization across schools, but particularly in cost-plus theories of pricing and supply (PKE); social and environmental costs valued in different ways across theories
Production costs			x		x				x	x			x		x	x	
Cost efficiency															x		
Labour costs					x												
Mechanization costs			x						x				x				
Social and environmental costs										x							

Dimensions, themes and <i>indicanda</i>	AcS et al. (2025)	CLIM-SAI (2014)	Craheix et al. (2016)	Heredia-R. et al. (2024)	Jones et al. (2024)	Meul et al. (2008)	Paracchini et al. (2015)	Peano et al. (2015)	Sadok et al. (2009)	Schader et al. (2016)	Talukder et al. (2017)	Thalmann and Grenz (2013)	Estienne et al. (2021)	Wezel et al. (2025)	Wilfart et al. (2023)	Zahm et al. (2024)	Theoretical alignment with different schools of thought		
Total production costs													x				(degrowth = political and plural valuation, OIE = institutional arrangements, NCE/NIE = shadow pricing)		
Transport costs																x			
Revenues			x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			Divergence of views: Behavioural assumptions (NCE = profit max., PKE = growth max.)	
Accounting profits			x	x			x		x	x	x			x				Degrowth views excessive profits as growth driver (i.e. unsustainable).	
Economic profits				x		x						x			x			Modelling of zero-growth scenarios results in lower rates of heterogenous profit that act distributionally.	
Market structure			x					x			x								
Returns to labour						x													
Returns to land													x						
Turnover												x			x				
Local economy and public provisioning	x		x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x							Locality does not feature in many theories except as a source of cost to be balanced against trade advantages.
Local employment			x					x	x	x		x							
Local procurement										x									
Public services and infrastructure						x				x	x								Direct public provisioning and public services emphasized by degrowth.
Tax contributions										x									Also questions traditional concepts of development as increases in income (rather than sustainable wellbeing)
Territorial development										x									
Value creation	x		x				x					x							
Cultural amenities						x		x											

4. Discussion

4.1 So, what is “economic sustainability” anyway?

In this study, I attempted to give an overview of a wide selection of theories of the firm in economics (i.e. a plural review). The goal was to investigate both orthodox and heterodox theories to gain a better understanding and definition of the term “economic sustainability”. To do this, I reviewed methods in sustainability assessment (particularly, farm-based SATs in the agri-food sector) and made tentative links to the issues and core factors emerging from the theoretical accounts. The results of the SAT review show a host of diverse sustainability themes proposed under the “economic dimension” of sustainability. Several groups of themes are well supported by a range of economic schools of thought. Others reveal core tensions between schools of thought. I discuss some of these conflicts below, starting with the most broadly supported themes and then moving to the more controversial.

The value of cooperation

For example, in the theme “Economic vulnerability” (Table 2), there would be little contradiction with diverse theories of the firm on the importance of stabilizing and diversifying income sources, managing risk and debt, maintaining liquidity and stability etc. Only the criterion of “solidarity and cooperation” appears at odds with numerous theories. Cooperation among firms is almost universally seen through the lens of collusion, apart from perhaps Marxian and Ecological Economics, where cooperation and solidarity play a larger role in how a sustainable economy should look like (e.g. Thompson 2016, Nesterova 2020, Froese et al. 2023).

Entrepreneurship and innovation

Across SATs, there was some reflection of aspects of entrepreneurship, such as capacity development, environmental and local knowledge, innovation and adoption as well as overall strategic sustainability management. On the one hand, this aligns strongly with Austrian theory in emphasizing that firms are engaged in a competition of discovery rather than optimization (Langlois 2013). However, metrics used to assess this were usually rudimentary and covered both the classic “entrepreneur” (e.g. the farm manager) as well as worker capacity development. Tool development would benefit from a more robust treatment of innovation and entrepreneurship as a basis for future indicators, which would align with the family of “Resource-Based View” theories to which the Austrian school belongs, although there are also various interpretations of this theory (Dietrich and Krafft 2012 Ch. 20).

Efficiency and productivity

While cost-efficiency and productivity are implicitly important to a range of schools of thought, there are interesting perspectives from both an Ecological and a Marxian perspective. With regards to productivity indicators, Ecological Economics strongly questions the sustainability of productivity increases, because these are usually accompanied (or directly caused) by increased material and energy intensity (e.g. automation, robotics, artificial intelligence). They highlight the fact that the Solow's (1957) "Total Factor Productivity" (TFP), held by Neoclassicals to be evidence of technical prowess, can actually be almost fully explained by the efficiency of extracting useful work out of available energy in both the USA and Japan (Ayres and Warr 2009). Furthermore, Keen et al. (2019) show a remarkably strong correlation between energy consumption and economic growth. If energy sources are fundamentally limited, then this also applies to growth (Ayres 2022). In a growth-constrained, capitalist market economy, productivity increases would have the effect of redistributing value rather than creating it (Jackson and Victor 2016, 2020), thus contributing to inequality. Policies for redistribution would be required to counter this effect, making indicators based on productivity somewhat contextual and unambiguous, which are not desirable qualities of an indicator (Niemeijer and de Groot 2008).

Profitability and growth

Another open question is on the role of "Revenues", namely profits (returns to capital), in the assessment of sustainability. Most theories would have no issue with profitability, however Marxian analysis would see profits as a redistribution from workers to capitalists and be fundamentally against it. They argue for removing the source of profits (ownership relations between capitalists and workers) by arguing for worker cooperatives (Thompson 2016) and economic planning. Ecological Economics also argues that the search for profits creates a growth imperative. Some debate as to whether profits can exist in a zero-growth economy at all and promote common ownership as a solution (e.g. Hinton 2020, 2021). However, the logic can also be reversed, that growth is a means of profits amongst many. As in numerous theories above (e.g. PKE), it is other factors such as competition and ownership regimes that causes growth rather than profitability *per se*. Zero-growth macroeconomic modelling has also demonstrated a downward trend in profits over time, but not the elimination of them (Jackson and Victor 2016). Others in degrowth recognize that it is not the generation of profits that drives growth, but their re-investment. As such they argue that profits must be consumed or redistributed (Nesterova 2020, Froese et al. 2023). A balanced view that accounts for ecological limits (which forms a key tenet of sustainability) would therefore probably argue for limited profits rather than unbounded profits (or simply cost coverage) as an operational measure of economic sustainability. This would have substantial implications for the development of SATs, which tend to treat higher revenues and profits as universally positive.

4.2 Conclusions

Due to space limitations, the full list of links between economic theory and SAT practice cannot be fully explored in this article. However, the analysis has shown that there is considerable tension surrounding the characterization of economic sustainability, and the theory certainly points to a much more plural view of sustainability, with definitions of the “economy” spanning at the classical “social”, “economic” and “governance” dimensions of sustainability (FAO 2014b). When institutional theories are considered (PKE, OIE, NIE), much of what is in the “governance” dimension, in how firms leverage power and influence within the institutional environment should be relocated to the economic dimension, in particular the reflection of power relationships both within and outside the firm. Power (via property) also features heavily in Marxist theory, which would also include currently “social sustainability” themes like worker exploitation, forced labour, working conditions etc. And a feminist perspective would also bring the gender dimension back into the economic. In the face of such diversity, it seems prudent to abandon the “three pillars” or “triple bottom line” approach to sustainability assessment (Purvis et al. 2019) in favour of a more unified and systemic alternative that integrated themes across “dimensions” into a single theoretical construct. To do that, however, would require resolving the numerous tensions between economic schools of thought.

Acknowledgements

The research was supported by a grant from the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) Sinergia programme (grant number CRSII5_202300).

5. References

- Acs, S., J. Costa Leite, E. Sanyé-Mengual, A. Caivano, R. Catarino, J.-N. Druon, F. Di Marcantonio, B. De Jong, I. Guerrero, P. Gurría, R. M'barek, P. Panagos, C. Puerta-Piñero, S. Tamosiunas, J. Wollgast, and K. Tóth. 2025. Towards sustainable food systems: developing a monitoring framework for the EU. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 8:1502081.
- Arias-Arévalo, P., E. Gómez-Baggethun, B. Martín-López, and M. Pérez-Rincón. 2018. Widening the Evaluative Space for Ecosystem Services: A Taxonomy of Plural Values and Valuation Methods. *Environmental Values* 27:29–53.
- Arrow, K. J. 1971. The Firm in General Equilibrium Theory. Pages 68–110 in R. Marris and A. Wood, editors. *The Corporate Economy: Growth, Competition, and Innovative Potential*. Palgrave Macmillan UK, London.
- Arulnathan, V., M. D. Heidari, M. Doyon, E. Li, and N. Pelletier. 2020. Farm-level decision support tools: A review of methodological choices and their consistency with principles of sustainability assessment. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 256:120410.
- Atkinson, G., I. Bateman, and S. Mourato. 2012. Recent advances in the valuation of ecosystem services and biodiversity. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy* 28:22–47.
- Ayres, R. U. 2022. The Economy as an “Island of Order” far from Equilibrium. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Ayres, R. U., and B. Warr. 2009. The economic growth engine: how energy and work drive material prosperity. Page *The Economic Growth Engine*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Binder, C. R., G. Feola, and J. K. Steinberger. 2010. Considering the normative, systemic and procedural dimensions in indicator-based sustainability assessments in agriculture. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review* 30:71–81.
- Bonisoli, L., E. Galdeano-Gómez, and L. Piedra-Muñoz. 2018. Deconstructing criteria and assessment tools to build agri-sustainability indicators and support farmers’ decision-making process. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 182:1080–1094.
- Braverman, H. 1998. *Labor and Monopoly Capital: The Degradation of Work in the Twentieth Century*. NYU Press.
- Brennan, D. M. 2017. The Capitalist Firm. Page *Routledge Handbook of Marxian Economics*. Routledge.
- Chopin, P., C. P. Mubaya, K. Descheemaeker, I. Öborn, and G. Bergkvist. 2021. Avenues for improving farming sustainability assessment with upgraded tools, sustainability framing and indicators. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development* 41:19.
- Christie, M., B. Martín-López, A. Church, E. Siwicka, P. Szymonczyk, and J. Mena Sauterel. 2019. Understanding the diversity of values of “Nature’s contributions to people”: insights from the IPBES Assessment of Europe and Central Asia. *Sustainability Science* 14:1267–1282.
- Clark, W. C., P. J. Crutzen, and H. J. Schellnhuber. 2005. Science for global sustainability: toward a new paradigm. Available at SSRN 702501.
- Coase, R. H. 1937. The nature of the firm (1937). *Economica* 4:386–405.

- Daly, H. E. 1992. Steady-State Economics: Concepts, Questions, Policies. *GAIA - Ecological Perspectives for Science and Society* 1:333–338.
- Daly, H. E. 1997a. Beyond growth: the economics of sustainable development. Beacon Pr.
- Daly, H. E. 1997b. Georgescu-Roegen versus Solow/Stiglitz. *Ecological Economics* 22:261–266.
- De Scitovszky, T. 1941. A note on welfare propositions in economics. *The Review of Economic Studies* 9:77–88.
- Debreu, G. 1959. *Theory of Value: An Axiomatic Analysis of Economic Equilibrium*. Yale University Press.
- Diesendorf, M., G. Davies, T. Wiedmann, J. H. Spangenberg, and S. Hail. 2024. Sustainability scientists' critique of neoclassical economics. *Global Sustainability* 7:e33.
- Dietrich, M., and J. Krafft. 2012. *Handbook on the Economics and Theory of the Firm*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, UK and Northampton, MA, USA.
- Earl, P. E. 2017. *Theory of the Firm*. Page Routledge Handbook of Ecological Economics. Routledge.
- Eichler Inwood, S. E., S. López-Ridaura, K. L. Kline, B. Gérard, A. G. Monsalve, B. Govaerts, and V. H. Dale. 2018. Assessing sustainability in agricultural landscapes: a review of approaches. *Environmental Reviews* 26:299–315.
- Eichner, A. S. 1976. *The Megacorp and Oligopoly: Micro Foundations of Macro Dynamics*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- FAO. 2014a. *Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture Systems (SAFA) Guidelines, Vers. 3*. Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), Rome.
- FAO. 2014b. *Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture systems (SAFA)*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Rome.
- FAO. 2018. *Transforming Food and Agriculture to Achieve the SDGs*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Farley, J. C., H. E. Daly, and J. D. Erickson. 2005. *Ecological economics: A workbook for problem-based learning*. Island Press.
- Froese, T., M. Richter, F. Hofmann, and F. Lüdeke-Freund. 2023. Degrowth-oriented organisational value creation: A systematic literature review of case studies. *Ecological Economics* 207:107765.
- Galbraith, J. K. 1967. *The New Industrial State*. Princeton University Press.
- Georgescu-Roegen, N. 1971. *The entropy law and the economic process*. Harvard University Press Cambridge, MA.
- Gräbner, C., and J. Kapeller. 2017. The micro—macro link in heterodox economics. Pages 145–159 in T.-H. Jo, L. Chester, and C. D'Ippoliti, editors. *The Routledge Handbook of Heterodox Economics*. First edition. Routledge, Abingdon, Oxon ; New York, NY : Routledge, 2017.
- Hankammer, S., R. Kleer, L. Mühl, and J. Euler. 2021. Principles for organizations striving for sustainable degrowth: Framework development and application to four B Corps. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 300:126818.
- Harvey, D. 2014. *Seventeen Contradictions and the End of Capitalism*. Oxford University Press.

- Heredia-R, M., I. Blanco-Gutiérrez, P. Esteve, L. Puhl, and C. Morales-Opazo. 2024. Assessment of sustainability in cocoa farms in Ecuador: application of a multidimensional indicator-based framework. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability* 22:2379863.
- Hicks, J. R. 1939. The Foundations of Welfare Economics. *The Economic Journal* 49:696–712.
- Hinton, J. 2021. Five key dimensions of post-growth business: Putting the pieces together. *Futures* 131:102761.
- Hinton, J. B. 2020. Fit for purpose? Clarifying the critical role of profit for sustainability. *Journal of Political Ecology* 27:236–262.
- Jackson, T. 2009. *Prosperity without Growth? - The transition to a sustainable economy.* Sustainable Development Commission, UK.
- Jackson, T., and P. A. Victor. 2016. Does slow growth lead to rising inequality? Some theoretical reflections and numerical simulations. *Ecological Economics* 121:206–219.
- Jackson, T., and P. A. Victor. 2020. The Transition to a Sustainable Prosperity-A Stock-Flow-Consistent Ecological Macroeconomic Model for Canada. *Ecological Economics* 177:106787.
- Jo, T.-H. 2019. The Institutionalist Theory of the Business Enterprise: Past, Present, and Future. *Journal of Economic Issues* 53:597–611.
- Kaldor, N. 1939. Welfare Propositions of Economics and Interpersonal Comparisons of Utility. *The Economic Journal* 49:549–552.
- Kalecki, M. 1939. *Essays in the Theory of Economic Fluctuations.* G. Allen & Unwin, Limited.
- Keen, S. 2013. Predicting the ‘Global Financial Crisis’: Post-Keynesian Macroeconomics. *Economic Record* 89:228–254.
- Keen, S., R. U. Ayres, and R. Standish. 2019. A Note on the Role of Energy in Production. *Ecological Economics* 157:40–46.
- Keynes, J. M. 1937. The General Theory of Employment. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 51:209–223.
- Knight, F. H. 1921. Cost of Production and Price over Long and Short Periods. *Journal of Political Economy* 29:304–335.
- Lampridi, M. G., C. G. Sørensen, and D. Bochtis. 2019. Agricultural Sustainability: A Review of Concepts and Methods. *Sustainability* 11:5120.
- Langlois, R. N. 2013. The Austrian theory of the firm: Retrospect and prospect. *The Review of Austrian Economics* 26:247–258.
- Lavoie, M. 2009. *Introduction to Post-Keynesian Economics.* Springer.
- Lavoie, M. 2022. *Post-Keynesian Economics: New Foundations.* Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Lee, F. S., and T.-H. Jo. 2018. *Microeconomic theory: a heterodox approach.* 1 Edition. Routledge, New York.
- Levitt, S. D., and S. J. Dubner. 2008. *Freakonomics.* INCA.
- Lewin, P., and S. E. Phelan. 2000. An Austrian Theory of the Firm. *Review of Austrian Economics* 13:59–79.
- Lozano, R., A. Carpenter, and D. Huisingh. 2015. A review of ‘theories of the firm’ and their contributions to Corporate Sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 106:430–442.
- Marshall, A. 1890. *Principles of Economics.* Eighth edition. Springer, Hampshire, UK.

- Martinez-Alier, J., G. Munda, and J. O'Neill. 1998. Weak comparability of values as a foundation for ecological economics. *Ecological economics* 26:277–286.
- Marx, K. 1999. *Capital: An Abridged Edition*. OUP Oxford.
- Mas-Colell, A., M. D. Whinston, and J. R. Green. 1995. *Microeconomic theory*. Oxford university press New York.
- Meadows, D. H., D. L. Meadows, J. Randers, W. W. Behrens, and R. C. of. 1972. *The limits to growth*. Universe Books New York.
- Means, G. C. 1972. The Administered-Price Thesis Reconfirmed. *The American Economic Review* 62:292–306.
- Minsky, H. P. 1975. *John Maynard Keynes*. Columbia University Press, New York.
- Minsky, H. P. 1986. *Stabilizing an Unstable Economy*. Yale University Press.
- von Mises, L. 1949. *Human action*. Ludwig von Mises Institute.
- Nesterova, I. 2020. Degrowth business framework: Implications for sustainable development. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 262:121382.
- Niemeijer, D., and R. S. de Groot. 2008. A conceptual framework for selecting environmental indicator sets. *Ecological Indicators* 8:14–25.
- North, D. C. 1990. *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*. Cambridge University Press.
- de Olde, E. M., M. Sautier, and J. Whitehead. 2018. Comprehensiveness or implementation: Challenges in translating farm-level sustainability assessments into action for sustainable development. *Ecological Indicators* 85:1107–1112.
- O'Neill, D. W., A. L. Fanning, W. F. Lamb, and J. K. Steinberger. 2018. A good life for all within planetary boundaries. *Nature Sustainability* 1:88.
- Paracchini, M. L., C. Bulgheroni, G. Borreani, E. Tabacco, A. Banterle, D. Bertoni, G. Rossi, G. Parolo, R. Origgi, and C. De Paola. 2015. A diagnostic system to assess sustainability at a farm level: The SOSTARE model. *Agricultural Systems* 133:35–53.
- Pintér, L., P. Hardi, A. Martinuzzi, and J. Hall. 2012. Bellagio STAMP: Principles for sustainability assessment and measurement. *Ecological Indicators* 17:20–28.
- Pirgmaier, E. 2017. The Neoclassical Trojan Horse of Steady-State Economics. *Ecological Economics* 133:52–61.
- Polanyi, K. 1944. *The Great Transformation: The Political and Economic Origins of Our Time*. 2nd ed. (2001). Beacon Press, Boston, Mass.
- Purvis, B., Y. Mao, and D. Robinson. 2019. Three pillars of sustainability: in search of conceptual origins. *Sustainability Science* 14:681–695.
- Richters, O., and A. Siemoneit. 2019. Growth imperatives: Substantiating a contested concept. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics* 51:126–137.
- Robbins, L. 1932. *An Essay on the Nature and Significance of Economic Science*. Ludwig von Mises Institute.
- Roemer, J. E. 2011. The Ethics of Intertemporal Distribution in a Warming Planet. *Environmental and Resource Economics* 48:363–390.

- Roesch, A., A. Nyfeler-Brunner, and G. Gaillard. 2021. Sustainability assessment of farms using SALCAsustain methodology. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*:S2352550921000609.
- Rothbard, M. N. 1962. 1970. *Man, Economy, and State: A Treatise on Economic Principles*. Los Angeles: Nash Publishing.
- Sala, S., B. Ciuffo, and P. Nijkamp. 2015. A systemic framework for sustainability assessment. *Ecological Economics* 119:314–325.
- Sala, S., F. Farioli, and A. Zamagni. 2013. Progress in sustainability science: lessons learnt from current methodologies for sustainability assessment: Part 1. *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 18:1653–1672.
- Schader, C., L. Baumgart, J. Landert, A. Muller, B. Ssebunya, J. Blockeel, R. Weissshaidinger, R. Petrasek, D. Mészáros, S. Padel, C. Gerrard, L. Smith, T. Lindenthal, U. Niggli, and M. Stolze. 2016. Using the Sustainability Monitoring and Assessment Routine (SMART) for the Systematic Analysis of Trade-Offs and Synergies between Sustainability Dimensions and Themes at Farm Level. *Sustainability* 8:274.
- Schader, C., J. Grenz, M. S. Meier, and M. Stolze. 2014. Scope and precision of sustainability assessment approaches to food systems. *Ecology and Society* 19.
- Schumpeter, J. A. 2000. *Entrepreneurship as Innovation*. SSRN Scholarly Paper, Social Science Research Network, Rochester, NY.
- Sen, A. 2005. Human Rights and Capabilities. *Journal of Human Development* 6:151–166.
- Shackle, G. L. S. 1972. *Epistemics and Economics*. Transaction Publishers, New Brunswick.
- Simon, H. A. 1955. A behavioral model of rational choice. *The quarterly journal of economics*:99–118.
- Solow, R. M. 1957. Technical Change and the Aggregate Production Function. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 39:312–320.
- Solow, R. M. 1974. The Economics of Resources or the Resources of Economics. *The American Economic Review* 64:1–14.
- Spangenberg, J. H. 2005. Economic sustainability of the economy: concepts and indicators. *International journal of sustainable development* 8:47–64.
- Spash, C. L. 2011. Social ecological economics: Understanding the past to see the future. *American Journal of Economics and Sociology* 70:340–375.
- Spash, C. L. 2013. The shallow or the deep ecological economics movement? *Ecological Economics* 93:351–362.
- Steffen, W., K. Richardson, J. Rockström, S. E. Cornell, I. Fetzer, E. M. Bennett, R. Biggs, S. R. Carpenter, W. de Vries, C. A. de Wit, C. Folke, D. Gerten, J. Heinke, G. M. Mace, L. M. Persson, V. Ramanathan, B. Reyers, and S. Sörlin. 2015. Planetary boundaries: Guiding human development on a changing planet. *Science*:1259855.
- Subedi, Y. R., C. Godde, P. Korale-Gedara, J. Farr, and S. Fyfe. 2025. Exploring the complexity of food systems assessments: A systematic literature review of frameworks and indicators. *Global Food Security* 46:100881.
- Thalmann, C., and J. Grenz. 2013. Factors Affecting the Implementation of Measures for Improving Sustainability on Farms Following the RISE Sustainability Evaluation. Pages

- 107–121 in A. A. Marta-Costa and E. L. D. G. Soares da Silva, editors. *Methods and Procedures for Building Sustainable Farming Systems: Application in the European Context*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht.
- Thompson, S. 2016. Worker Cooperatives in the Theory of the Firm: Marx and Veblen on Technological Determinism. *Journal of Economic Issues*.
- Tirole, J. 1988. *The Theory of Industrial Organization*. MIT Press.
- Veblen, T. 1904. *The Theory of Business Enterprise*. The New York American Library.
- de Vries, B. J. M. 2012. *Sustainability Science*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Walker, P. 2016. *The Theory of the Firm: An overview of the economic mainstream*. Routledge, London.
- Wiedmann, T. O., H. Schandl, M. Lenzen, D. Moran, S. Suh, J. West, and K. Kanemoto. 2013. The material footprint of nations. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*:201220362.
- Williams, P. L. 1978. *The emergence of the theory of the firm: from Adam Smith to Alfred Marshall*. Springer.
- Williamson, O. E. 1975. *Markets and Hierarchies, Analysis and Antitrust Implications: A Study in the Economics of Internal Organization*. Free Press.
- Williamson, O. E. 1985. *The Economic Institutions of Capitalism*. Simon and Schuster.
- Zahm, F., A. A. Ugaglia, J.-M. Barbier, D. Carayon, B. Del’homme, M. Gafsi, P. Gasselín, C. Gestin, S. Girard, L. Guichard, C. Loyce, V. Manneville, B. Redlingshöfer, and I. Rodrigues. 2024. Assessing farm sustainability: the IDEA4 method, a conceptual framework combining dimensions and properties of sustainability. *Cahiers Agricultures* 33:10.

6. Appendix

6.1 Sustainability frameworks

Table 3. Sustainability assessment tools (SATs) included in the analysis

Reference	Acronym	Full name	Full citation
Acs et al. (2025)	EUFSSMF	EU Food System Sustainability Monitoring Framework	Acs, S., J. Costa Leite, E. Sanyé-Mengual, A. Caivano, R. Catarino, J.-N. Druon, F. Di Marcantonio, B. De Jong, I. Guerrero, P. Gurría, R. M'barek, P. Panagos, C. Puerta-Piñero, S. Tamosiunas, J. Wollgast, and K. Tóth. 2025. Towards sustainable food systems: developing a monitoring framework for the EU. <i>Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems</i> 8.
Craheix et al. (2016)	MASC	Multicriteria Assessment of the Sustainability of Cropping Systems	Craheix, D., F. Angevin, T. Doré, and S. de Tourdonnet. 2016. Using a multicriteria assessment model to evaluate the sustainability of conservation agriculture at the cropping system level in France. <i>European Journal of Agronomy</i> 76:75–86.
Heredia-R. et al. (2024)	FARMTO OLS	None	Heredia-R, M., I. Blanco-Gutiérrez, P. Esteve, L. Puhl, and C. Morales-Opazo. 2024. Assessment of sustainability in cocoa farms in Ecuador: application of a multidimensional indicator-based framework. <i>International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability</i> 22:2379863.
Jones et al. (2026)	HOLPA	Holistic Localized Performance Assessment	Jones, S. K., A. C. Sánchez Bogado, C. Lamanna, C. Dickens, M. S. Geck, C. Wickramaratne, V. Alary, P. Bolo, D. J. Choruma, S. Douangsavanh, M. G. Fall, G. Falconnier, S. Gupta, C. Kettle, S. Krishnan, S. S. Nyawira, G. Orjuela-Ramirez, B. M. Orounladi, P. Pareja, and T. Sibanda. 2024. Holistic Localized Performance Assessment (HOLPA) Tool for Collecting Locally Relevant and Globally Comparable Evidence of Agroecology's Effects on Nature and People. SSRN.
Meul et al. (2008)	MOTIFS	MONitoring Tool for Integrated Farm Sustainability	Meul, M., S. Van Passel, F. Nevens, J. Dessein, E. Rogge, A. Mulier, and A. Van Hauwermeiren. 2008. MOTIFS: a monitoring tool for integrated farm sustainability. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> 28:321–332.

Mottet et al. (2020)	TAPE	A Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation	Mottet, A., A. Bicksler, D. Lucantoni, F. De Rosa, B. Scherf, E. Scopel, S. López-Ridaura, B. Gemmil-Herren, R. Bezner Kerr, J.-M. Sourisseau, P. Petersen, J.-L. Chotte, A. Loconto, and P. Tittonell. 2020. Assessing Transitions to Sustainable Agricultural and Food Systems: A Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE). <i>Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems</i> 4:579154.
Paracchini et al. (2015)	SOSTARE	Analysis of farm technical efficiency and impacts on environmental and economic sustainability	Paracchini, M. L., C. Bulgheroni, G. Borreani, E. Tabacco, A. Banterle, D. Bertoni, G. Rossi, G. Parolo, R. Origgi, and C. De Paola. 2015. A diagnostic system to assess sustainability at a farm level: The SOSTARE model. <i>Agricultural Systems</i> 133:35–53.
Peano et al. (2015)	SAEMETH	Sustainable Agri-Food Evaluation Methodology	Peano, C., N. Tecco, E. Dansero, V. Girgenti, and F. Sottile. 2015. Evaluating the Sustainability in Complex Agri-Food Systems: The SAEMETH Framework. <i>Sustainability</i> 7:6721–6741.
Petersen et al. (2020)	Lume	None	Petersen, P., L. Silveira, G. B. Fernandes, and S. G. de Almeida. 2020. Lume: a method for the economic-ecological analysis of agroecosystems. Centre for Agroecology, Water and Resilience (CAWR). Coventry University, Coventry.
Sadok et al. (2009)	MASC	Multi-Attribute Sustainability Criteria	Sadok, W., F. Angevin, J.-E. Bergez, C. Bockstaller, B. Colomb, L. Guichard, R. Reau, A. Messéan, and T. Doré. 2009. MASC, a qualitative multi-attribute decision model for ex ante assessment of the sustainability of cropping systems. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> 29:447–461.
Schader et al. (2016)	SMART-Farm	Sustainability Monitoring and Assessment RouTine	Schader, C., L. Baumgart, J. Landert, A. Muller, B. Ssebunya, J. Blockeel, R. Weissheidinger, R. Petrasek, D. Mészáros, S. Padel, C. Gerrard, L. Smith, T. Lindenthal, U. Niggli, and M. Stolze. 2016. Using the Sustainability Monitoring and Assessment Routine (SMART) for the Systematic Analysis of Trade-Offs and Synergies between Sustainability Dimensions and Themes at Farm Level. <i>Sustainability</i> 8:274.
Talukder et al. (2017)	None	None	Talukder, B., A. Blay-Palmer, K. W. Hipel, and G. W. vanLoon. 2017. Elimination Method of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA): A Simple Methodological

			Approach for Assessing Agricultural Sustainability. Sustainability 9:287.
Thalmann and Grenz (2013)	RISE	Response Induced Sustainability Evaluation	Thalmann, C., and J. Grenz. 2013. Factors Affecting the Implementation of Measures for Improving Sustainability on Farms Following the RISE Sustainability Evaluation. Pages 107–121 in A. A. Marta-Costa and E. L. D. G. Soares da Silva, editors. Methods and Procedures for Building Sustainable Farming Systems: Application in the European Context. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht.
Trivino-Tarradas et al. (2019)	INSPIA	Initiative for Sustainable Productive Agriculture	Trivino-Tarradas, P., M. R. Gomez-Ariza, G. Basch, and E. J. Gonzalez-Sanchez. 2019. Sustainability Assessment of Annual and Permanent Crops: The Inspia Model. Sustainability 11:738.
Van Cauwenbergh et al. (2007)	SAFE	Sustainability Assessment of Farming and the Environment	Van Cauwenbergh, N., K. Biala, C. Biielders, V. Brouckaert, L. Franchois, V. Garcia Ciudad, M. Hermy, E. Mathijs, B. Muys, J. Reijnders, X. Sauvenier, J. Valckx, M. Vanclooster, B. Van der Veken, E. Wauters, and A. Peeters. 2007. SAFE—A hierarchical framework for assessing the sustainability of agricultural systems. Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment 120:229–242.
Estienne et al. (2021)	SYSTERRE	None	Estienne, M., L. Casal, S. Cadoux, and T. Clotilde. (n.d.). Cropping system diversification including intercropping: Learnings from Syppre devices and SYSTERRE multi-criteria assessment.
Wezel et al. (2025)	OASIS	Original Agroecological Survey and Indicator System	Wezel, A., P. Migliorini, A. Brumer, T. Gaifami, A. Marchetti, G. Floymont, G. Guizard, E. Michel, M.-A. Renaud, K. Škorjanc, N. Allard, S. Bocchi, and A. Peeters. 2025. Application of the Original Agroecological Survey and Indicator System tool (OASIS) to organic and conventional farms in Belgium, France, and Italy. Frontiers in Agronomy 7.
Wilfart et al. (2023)	DEXi-Dairy	Decision Expert Dairy	Wilfart, A., V. Baillet, L. Balaine, X. D. de Otálora, F. Dragoni, D. J. Krol, J. Frątczak-Müller, A. Rychła, D. G. P. Rodriguez, J. Breen, V. Anestis, C. Buckley, H. Alem, W. Winiwarter, N. Akkal-Corfini, and B. Amon. 2023. DEXi-Dairy: an ex post multicriteria tool to assess the sustainability of dairy production systems in various

			European regions. <i>Agronomy for Sustainable Development</i> 43:82.
Zahm et al. (2024)	IDEA (v.4)	Indicateurs de Durabilité des Exploitations Agricoles [FR]	Zahm, F., A. A. Ugaglia, J.-M. Barbier, D. Carayon, B. Del'homme, M. Gafsi, P. Gasselin, C. Gestin, S. Girard, L. Guichard, C. Loyce, V. Manneville, B. Redlingshöfer, and I. Rodrigues. 2024. Assessing farm sustainability: the IDEA4 method, a conceptual framework combining dimensions and properties of sustainability. <i>Cahiers Agricultures</i> 33:10.